

Data management plan (DMP)

**SYNTHESIS OF A BIO-
SURFACTANT FROM *Parinari
polyandra* SEED OIL**

Version	Effective date	Description of document/changes
1.0	29/11/2024	First version of the DMP – created for the start of the project

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List of acronyms

DMP	data management plan
RDM	research data management
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Introduction

Science Europe practical guide, FAIR data

A DMP is a structured document that keeps record of what research data is created and what happens to that data during and after a project. It helps with planning the research process and defining responsibilities in a research project involving several researchers or institutions.

For writing this DMP, we followed [the recommendations of Science Europe](#) as they reflect the guidelines agreed upon by the major funders in Europe.

To make our data FAIR, they generally will be treated according to the following criteria:

- We will make our data findable, by uploading it to a data repository that provides a persistent identifier, and adding relevant metadata.
- We will make our data accessible by providing open access to data, wherever possible. In cases, where open access is not possible, we will provide meaningful metadata plus contact information for access requests.
- We will make our data interoperable by providing and describing data in a way that is common within our domain by using the same file formats, schemas and vocabularies. We will provide good documentation for all our datasets.
- We will make our data reusable by adding metadata and comprehensive Readme files to all published datasets. The descriptions include details on the methodology used, analytical and procedural information. In case of publication, licenses for code and data will always be assigned and clearly marked.

Relevant Policies and Guidelines

- TU Wien Policy for Research Data Management: <https://www.tuwien.at/index.php?eID=dms&s=4&path=Directives%20and%20Regulations%20of%20the%20Rectorate/Policy%20for%20Research%20Data%20Management.pdf>
- TU Wien Code of Conduct – Rules to Ensure Good Scientific Practice: <https://www.tuwien.at/index.php?eID=dms&s=4&path=Directives%20and%20Regulations%20of%20the%20Rectorate/Code%20of%20Conduct%20E2%80%93%20Rules%20to%20Ensure%20Good%20Scientific%20Practice.pdf>
- Directives and Regulations of the TU Wien Rectorate: <https://www.tuwien.at/en/tu-wien/organisation/central-divisions/data-protection-and-document-management/directives-regulations/>
- TU Wien Data Protection: <https://www.tuwien.at/en/tu-wien/organisation/central-divisions/data-protection-and-document-management/data-protection-at-tu-wien>
- Other (e.g. from a project partner)

1. Data description

1a Lists of datasets that will be reused or produced

Produced datasets

dataset ID	title	type	format	estimated volume	contains sensitive data
P1	Antioxidant activity of extracted oil and synthesized bio-surfactant.xlsx	Microsoft Excel document	xlsx	50KB	no
P2	SLS-FTIR	Raw data	pdf	500KB	no
P3	SPAR-FTIR	Raw data	pdf	500KB	no
P4	Surface-active properties.xlsx	Microsoft Excel document	xlsx	50KB	no

1b Data generation and reuse

Methods and software used for data generation and reuse

The research data will be generated using standard laboratory procedures. The oil will be extracted using soxhlet extraction procedure. The synthesised bio-surfactant and the synthetic surfactant, sodium lauryl sulphate will be analysed using FTIR (Fourier Transfer Infrared Spectroscopy) to confirm the functional groups present in them.

2. Documentation and data quality

2a Data organisation, metadata and documentation

The respective work package leader will handle the structure and versioning of the research data.

As there are no domain specific metadata standards applicable, we will provide a README file with an explanation of all values and terms used at file level. This will help others to identify, discover and reuse our data.

Additionally, we will provide common metadata such as title, description or keywords when publishing data in open access repositories. In such a case, we will follow the default template provided by the repository.

As far as possible, we will use controlled vocabularies for our data to allow inter-disciplinary interoperability and machine-actionability.

The datasets will be provided using excel files containing laboratory measurement in xls format (this will not exceed 50KB). Spectroscopy results will be provided in pdf format (this will not exceed 500KB).

2b Data quality control

The following data quality checks will be done: repeated samples or measurements, and peer review of data.

3. Storage and backup during research process

3a Storage and backup facilities

For the duration of the project, storage and backup of data will be ensured by the project manager in cooperation with the responsible representative of TU.it. The infrastructure of TU Wien will be used for this purpose.

P1 (Antioxidant activity of extracted oil and synthesized bio-surfactant.xlsx), P2 (SLS-FTIR), P3 (SPAR-FTIR), P4 (Surface-active properties.xlsx) will be stored on TU Wien Test Instance. Test Instance is an institutional repository of TU Wien to enable storing, sharing and publishing of digital objects, in particular research data. It is developed by the TU Wien Center for Research Data Management and hosted by TU.it. The repository uses persistent identifiers and synchronises with data hubs: DataCite, OpenAIRE, and BASE.

3b Data security and protection of sensitive data

We pay strict attention to compliance with the relevant institutional and national data protection policies listed in the introduction of this document. At this stage, it is not foreseen to process any sensitive data in the project. If this changes, advice will be sought from the data protection specialist at TU Wien, and the DMP will be updated.

Access to data during research:

dataset ID	selected project members	all other project members	the public
P1	writing	reading only	no access
P2	writing	reading only	no access
P3	writing	reading only	no access
P4	writing	reading only	no access

All incidents will be handled individually by an incident response team that is maintaining the affected service.

4. Legal and ethical requirements

4a Personal data

At this stage, it is not foreseen to process any personal data in the project. If this changes, advice will be sought from the data protection specialist at TU Wien, and the DMP will be updated.

4b Intellectual property rights and ownership

There are no legal restrictions on the processing and disclosure of our data.

4c Ethical issues

No particular ethical issue is foreseen with the data to be used or produced by the project. This section will be updated if issues arise.

5. Data sharing and long-term preservation

5a Data publication and access conditions

As far as possible, obtained datasets will be published in repositories. Details on access conditions, reuse licenses, reasons for restrictions, etc. are collected in the table below.

dataset ID	access conditions	restrictions / embargo reasons	estimated publication date	location for publication (repository)	PID	license
P1	Open	None	2024-11-29	TU Wien Research Data	DOI 10.70124/n2ak7-vbq40	CC-BY-4.0
P2	Open	None	2024-11-29	TU Wien Research Data	DOI 10.70124/n2ak7-vbq40	CC-BY-4.0
P3	Open	None	2024-11-29	TU Wien Research Data	DOI 10.70124/n2ak7-vbq40	CC-BY-4.0
P4	Open	None	2024-11-29	TU Wien Research Data	DOI 10.70124/n2ak7-vbq40	CC-BY-4.0

TU Wien Research Data is an institutional repository of TU Wien to enable storing, sharing and publishing of digital objects, in particular research data. It facilitates the funders' requirements for open access to research data and the FAIR principles by making research output findable, accessible, interoperable, and reusable. A DOI is assigned to each dataset published in TU Wien Research Data. This service is developed by the TU Wien Center for Research Data Management and hosted by TU.it. <https://researchdata.tuwien.at/>

Methods or software needed to access and use data: Microsoft Excel and a pdf viewer is required to access and reuse data.

5b Long-term preservation and deletion of data

dataset ID	location for long-term storage	minimum retention period (≥ 10 years)	foreseeable research uses and/or users
P1	TU Wien Research Data	10 years	Member of the scientific community, decision makers in industry, students and general public.
P2	TU Wien Research Data	10 years	
P3	TU Wien Research Data	10 years	
P4	TU Wien Research Data	10 years	

6. RDM responsibilities and resources

6a RDM-roles and responsibilities

The [PI / data officer XY] will direct the data management process overall, with the research assistants responsible for ensuring metadata production, day-to-day cross-checks, back-up and other quality control activities are maintained.

6b Resources

There are no costs dedicated to data management and ensuring that data will be FAIR.

Cost name	Cost type	Description	Unit	Value
Estimated total costs				0

Coverage of costs

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